

**A CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL
RELATIONSHIPS: A CASE STUDY OF THE MODERN
RUSSO-JAPANESE COUPLES**

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Abstract

Gender equality is a widely discussed topic to some extent. However, when it comes to domestic violence (DV), gender-based violence (GBV), or any form of abuse, society, and its authorities, represented by the government, are often hesitant to openly discuss these issues, particularly when international migrants and local citizens are involved. Japan is no exception. Therefore, the primary objective of this study is to understand the background and depict the current situation regarding the issue of abuse and domestic violence between Japanese citizens and Russian-speaking expatriates. The author applied either qualitative or quantitative approaches to provide a comprehensive explanation to the issue. This was achieved by presenting the results of the survey in figures or analyzing the data from in-depth interviews and open-ended questions surveys. Additionally, the author used critical discourse analysis to gain further insights into the topic. This manuscript mainly focuses on one side of the research based on open-ended and quantitative surveys, which collected data from 82 participants (male and female). The sample size was calculated from an estimated population of 9378 Russian-speaking expatriates living in Japan (n=9378). The quota sampling method aimed to divide the entire population of participants into meaningful clusters based on gender to provide more information. Finally, the research identified significant obstacles faced by these households and examined the concepts of freedom, safety, and abuse within them.

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The issue of domestic violence and gender inequality has been recognized and discussed for many decades. In 1975, the United Nations declared the International Women's Year, which brought these issues to the global stage. The Beijing Declaration in 1979 further highlighted these issues. In the 21st century, the announcement of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals in 2016 once again brought global attention to the problem of gender inequality. As a result, all 193 member states of the United Nations are now committed to achieving SDG5 (gender equality).

Through the efforts of feminists and suffragettes, many countries now recognize the importance of equal rights between men and women, such as voting rights, the right to participate in political life, reproductive rights, access to jobs and education, and equal representation in leadership positions. They are also highlighting the importance of preventing and solving gender-based violence (GBV), domestic violence (DV), abuse, harassment, gender bias, or any other gender-based discriminations in society (Fig. 1).

When it comes to the topic of GBV, DV, or abuse, it can be assumed that some of these problems are addressed in the world and in Japan. For instance, Japan has been making progress in preventing and controlling DV and GBV. The country is taking legal measures, providing support services, and holding education or/and awareness campaigns.

On the other hand, despite Japan's efforts, there are still significant obstacles to overcome. One of these is the inadequate attention paid to domestic violence in international households. Specifically, there is a lack of research on domestic violence between Japanese and Russian-speaking expatriates and limited data or national statistics on such abuse in these households. Additionally, there is a lack of scientific research on the specificities of such marriages.

Therefore, it is necessary to underline that this study primarily focused on three related and intertwined problems (Fig. 1.) **First**, the spread of feminism and its correlation with gender inequality in modern Japan. **Second**, the current situation regarding GBV, DV, or abuse in Japan among Japanese populations. **Third**, the problem of violence and abuse as well as analysis of cultural peculiarities, the concept

of freedom, safety and abuse between Japanese citizens and Russian-speaking expatriates (primarily focusing on the female Russian-speaking population living in Japan). The third topic will be widely illustrated in this manuscript.

Figure 1. The framework of the study: highlighting the main topics © author

In order to provide a detailed explanation to this issue the author applied either qualitative or quantitative analysis in this study. However, this manuscript primarily focuses on the qualitative approach. An online open-ended questionnaire survey was designed to gain in-depth information about participants` opinion, their reasonings and motivations regarding the issues of DV and abuse in international households. Furthermore, the questionnaire aimed to identify their attitude and response to violence and abuse. It was applied among 82 participants (sample size was calculated with a confidence level of 90%¹²). 82 participants who are representing different subgroups

¹² The $n (=9378)$ is the size of the population represented by Russian-speaking residents in Japan. The figures from statistics on foreign national residents covered by the immigration control and

were non-randomly (by quota-sampling and a snow-ball sampling methods) chosen for the survey. The age ranged from 20 to 60 years old. The interview ranged in terms of social class, race, and gender. It was conducted in the Russian language only.

Furthermore, the in-depth interview was based on a previous survey conducted by the author. To investigate the details of international marriages between Russian-speaking expatriates and Japanese citizens in Japan, as well as the specifics of verbal, economic, emotional, physical, and sexual abuse and violence in these families, the interview research method was applied. The interview was conducted with 17 respondents, who were non-randomly selected out of 82 survey participants.

Finally, in order to protect personal information and follow interview research ethics, the author followed the *regulation of (the EU) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, the Code of Ethics of the Japan Association for Social Research* (Jap. 一般社団法人社会調査協会 倫理規程), and *Kyoto University Policy on Research Data Management and Sharing*. This study was conducted with the awareness of the right and importance of protecting personal data. The researcher respects all fundamental rights and observes the freedoms of participants, letting them withdraw their positions anytime they need to.

In conclusion, this study aimed to collect additional information on women/men to analyze how they react and cope with violence or abuse and how they interpret it. Interview/survey candidates included male and female respondents who had supposedly experienced DV or abuse in some capacity or publicly acknowledged having been or currently being a victim of any form of DV or abuse. The interviews

refugee recognition act of the end of 2019 indicated that there were 9378 foreign Russian-speaking residents in Japan (The "Russian-speaking migrants" column in Japan contains immigrants from Ukraine, Belarus and Russia without providing any separation by language, culture or country. Foreign students who have the designation of "international student" are not included in these figures).

were conducted to explore the peculiarities of the marriage, the history of the couples, and their backgrounds. Second, to identify what violence means to them. Identifying and analyzing the individuals' trauma or perception of abuse was another goal of the interview/survey. Finally, this study set a goal to investigate the idea of freedom and how it coexists with abuse or/and DV.

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